

Supplemental Data for:

ACTH Stimulation Maximizes the Accuracy of Peripheral Steroid Profiling in Primary Aldosteronism Subtyping

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Supplemental Data

Supplemental table 1. List of measured steroids by LC-MS/MS and corresponding internal standards

Steroid	Manufacturer	IS	IS Manufacturer
18OHF	IsoSciences	18OHF-d4	IsoSciences
18oxoF	CGS	18OHF-d4	IsoSciences
Aldosterone	Cerilliant	Aldosterone-d8	Steraloids
18OHB	Sigma-Aldrich	Cortisone-d7	Cerilliant
Corticosterone	Cerilliant	Corticosterone-d8	C/D/N Isotopes
DOC	Cerilliant	DOC-d8	Sigma-Aldrich
Cortisol	Cerilliant	Cortisol-d4	Cerilliant
Cortisone	Cerilliant	Cortisone-d7	Cerilliant
11dF	Cerilliant	11dF-d5	Sigma-Aldrich
17OHP4	Cerilliant	17OHP4-d8	C/D/N Isotopes
Progesterone	Cerilliant	Progesterone-d9	C/D/N Isotopes
Testosterone	Cerilliant	Testosterone-d3	C/D/N Isotopes
A4	Cerilliant	A4-d7	Cambridge Isotopes
11OHT	Steraloids	11KT-d3	RTI
11KT	Steraloids	11KT-d3	RTI
11OHA	Steraloids	11OHA-d3	RTI
11KA	Steraloids	11OHA-d3	RTI

LC-MS/MS, liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry; IS, internal standard; 18OHF, 18-hydroxycortisol; 18oxoF, 18-oxocortisol; 18OHB, 18-hydroxycorticosterone; DOC, 11-deoxycorticosterone; 11dF, 11-deoxycortisol; 17OHP4, 17 α -hydroxyprogesterone; A4, androstenedione; 11OHT, 11 β -hydroxytestosterone; 11KT, 11-ketotestosterone; 11OHA, 11 β -hydroxyandrostenedione; 11KA, 11-ketoandrostenedione; RTI, The National Heart, Lung and Blood Institute RTI International metabolite Standards Synthesis Center.

Supplemental table 2. Demographic and clinical characteristics of patients with APAs

	<i>KCNJ5</i>	No <i>KCNJ5</i>	P values
N	27	12	
Age (yrs)	49 [43, 63]	55 [42, 66]	0.39
Men (N, %)	11 (40.7%)	10 (83.3%)	0.01
BMI (kg/m ²)	23.6 [21.6, 25.6]	26.5 [24.9, 28.6]	0.008
Systolic BP (mmHg)	133 [124, 148]	150 [139, 161]	0.02
Diastolic BP (mmHg)	86 [77, 94]	97 [75, 101]	0.10
AHTs (n)	1.0 [1.0, 2.0]	2.0 [1.5, 3.0]	0.16
Serum potassium (mM)	3.8 [3.6, 4.2]	3.9 [3.4, 4.1]	0.61
Potassium replacement (N, %)	25 (92.6%)	10 (83.3%)	0.38
eGFR (mL/min/1.73m ²)	79 [69, 88]	88 [69, 91]	0.41
PAC (ng/dL)	40.4 [29.2, 59.9]	32.7 [23.9, 41.8]	0.22
PRA (ng/mL/h)	0.30 [0.20, 0.30]	0.30 [0.20, 0.35]	0.75
ARR (ng/dL per ng/mL/h)	142.7 [79.8, 256.2]	110.3 [79.5, 191.0]	0.60
Urinary aldosterone (μg/day)	26.6 [17.7, 36.6]	26.5 [19.0, 29.3]	0.74
Cortisol after DST (μg/dL)	0.80 [0.70, 1.18]	0.80 [0.60, 1.00]	0.67

APA, aldosterone-producing adenoma; PA, primary aldosteronism; BMI, body mass index; BP, blood pressure; AHT, antihypertensive agents; eGFR, estimated glomerular filtration ratio; PAC, plasma aldosterone concentration; PRA, plasma renin activity; ARR, aldosterone-to-renin ratio; DST, 1 mg dexamethasone suppression test. Of the 40 unilateral PA cases, 1 case had no adrenal tissue available for research. The “No *KCNJ5*” group includes: 6 *CACNAID*-mutated, 1 *ATP1A1*-mutated, 2 *ATP2B3*-mutated, 1 *CTNNB1*-mutated APA cases, and 2 APA cases with no known mutations. Comparisons between the two groups were assessed with the Mann-Whitney *U* test for continuous variables, and the Chi-squared test for categorical variables. Continuous variables are shown as median [interquartile range].

Supplemental figure. Comparisons of receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curves between each studied state for discriminating between the two PA subtypes by individual steroids

PA, primary aldosteronism; 18OHB, 18-hydroxycorticosterone; 18oxoF, 18-oxocortisol; 18OHF, 18-hydroxycortisol. ROC curves shown represent steroids measured: in the morning (black); at midnight (grey); 15 (yellow), 30 (orange), 60 (red) minutes following cosyntropin stimulation; and after 1mg dexamethasone suppression (blue).